

EXPLORING THE FINANCIAL VIABILITY OF THE SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER PLANT PROJECT FOR THE ELECTRIFICATION OF THE MAROVOAY DISTRICT, BOENY REGION, MADAGASCAR

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Executive Summary :

Madagascar possesses significant renewable resources, but its electrification rate remains low at only 36%. Specifically, 74% of urban and only 15% of rural people have access to electricity. The Marovoay solar project, with a capacity of 5.9 MW, is designed to contribute to rural electrification. According to the financial analysis carried out using the FINPLAN tool, the project has an NPV of 531.59 million Malagasy Ariary (MGA) and an IRR of 10.37%, indicating its viability. However, it remains sensitive to fluctuations in tariffs and discount rates, and the use of over 2000 MGA in the price guarantees its viability. Profitability is optimal at a discount rate of 6%, but declines at higher rates, highlighting the need for rigorous cost and price management. Extending the construction period to five years could also offer financial benefits, but a thorough analysis of costs and risks is recommended. To ensure success, the government needs to introduce proactive price regulation, control investment, promote affordable prices and encourage risk management strategies such as revenue diversification, long-term contracts and the integration of hybrid technologies. A stable regulatory framework is essential to strengthen the financial resilience of the project, promote access to sustainable energy and support Madagascar's economic development.

1. Introduction

Madagascar boasts abundant renewable energy resources, including hydropower, solar, and wind, yet struggles with limited energy access. Only 36% of the population has electricity specifically, 74% of urban and only 15% of rural people have access to electricity. Most still depend on traditional biomass. This energy deficit, compounded by

outdated infrastructure, frequent outages, and reliance on imported fossil fuels, hampers economic growth, affects livelihoods, increases poverty, and leads to environmental degradation. To address these challenges, Madagascar has set ambitious goals for 2030: expanding renewable energy capacity to 893 MW, increasing electricity access to 80%, and promoting 50% adoption of clean cooking technologies (Reference?). Projects such as the Marovoay solar plant aim to improve rural energy access and foster sustainable development. Located in the Boeny Region, the Marovoay project will serve several communes through a 5.9 MW stand-alone solar PV plant, equipped with 27,484.8 kWh of storage batteries to ensure reliable power. Electricity will be distributed via medium and low-voltage networks, supporting local development. A financial analysis using FinPlan will evaluate the project's economic viability across various scenarios to assess net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), and other financial indicators. The project aligns with the National Energy Pact, SDG7, and the EMP-A initiative supporting energy planning in Africa.

Figure 1-2. Madagascar's electric energy profile for the year 2024 (Source: ORE 2024)

2. Methodology

2.1. Site/case study

This study concerns the installation of a stand-alone off-grid solar photovoltaic power plant with a total installed capacity of 5.967 MWp (or 5.9 MW), accompanied by a battery storage system with a total capacity of 27,484.8 kWh. The Marovoay rural electrification project is located in Oeust, Madagascar, in the Boeny region, within the district and rural commune of Marovoay.

Figure 3: Marovoay Location

Table 1. Marovoay Solar Power Plant Characteristics and Financing Arrangements:

PROJECT OVERVIEW	
CAPACITY	5.9 MV
CONSTRUCTION PERIOD	2 YEARS (2024 to 2025)
YEAR OF FIRST OPERATION	2026
LIFESPAN	25 YEARS
INVESTMENT	25,200 Million MGA
FINANCING STRUCTURE	EQUITY: 9628 Millions MGA SUBSIDIES : 15,572 Millions MGA
FINANCIAL ASSUMPTIONS	Inflation was steady at 7.6%, Discount rate was at 10%
FINANCING CURRENCY	LOCAL (MGA)
REVENUE PROJECTIONS	Electricity sales at MGA 2,000 and Producing Power PV field around 1491 kWp annually with storage 5177.5 kWh
TAXES	INCOME 20%

2.2 Modeling Approach/Tool Implemented

The financial analysis employs FINPLAN, a tool for strategic planning and decision-making. It analyzes data from the construction and operation phases of a solar photovoltaic power plant, including investment costs, operational expenses, revenue from energy sales, taxes, subsidies, and equity details. A model forecasts cash flows over the project's lifespan, considering electricity production, efficiency, maintenance, expenses, depreciation, inflation, and energy prices. FINPLAN calculates NPV and IRR to assess profitability. Additionally, the model calculates key ratios such as leverage, break-even point, debt service coverage ratio (DSCR), and debt-equity ratio. It also evaluates the project's financial robustness and risk exposure.

2.3 Sensitivity analysis

This financial analysis evaluates the sensitivity of NPV and IRR, reflecting shareholder dividends, to three key parameters:

- electricity price fluctuations (-25%, +25%, +50%),
- discount rate changes (6%, 8%, 10% and 12%),
- and the variation on the construction periods (2, 3, 5 years).

The study will assess project feasibility under these scenarios, highlighting the impact of each parameter on key indicators.

Table 2. Sensitivity analysis of key parameters evaluated

Sensitivity analysis	Sensitivity explanation	Assumptions Governing Scenarios	Parameters Studied
Sensitivity Variation One. on electricity Price	Price reduction by 25%, price increase by 25% and 50%	The Base power price MGA 2,000 is average for the rural market in Madagascar	Price Profitability (NPV and IRR) Shareholder Dividends
Sensitivity Variation Two. on Discount Rate	Varying by 6%, 8%, and 12%	The discount rate used corresponds to the standard rate in Madagascar, which is set at 10%.	
Sensitivity Variation Three. on the construction period	The construction period varies, ranging from 3 years, to 5 years	Restructuring the construction schedule could result in lower costs for consumers. The base construction period is 2 years.	

3. Results

3.1 Sensitivity One. Effect of a change price in Electricity on project profitability

This analysis examines the sensitivity of the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to changes in price, using a reference price of MGA 2,000 (100%), which gives an NPV of MGA 531.59 million and an IRR of 10.37%. A 25% decrease in price (to MGA 1,500) results in an NPV of MGA -3,857.38 million and an IRR of 6.8%, indicating that the project is close to breakeven. Conversely, a 25% increase (to MGA 2,500) increases the NPV to MGA +5,146.71 million and the IRR to 13.24%, while a 50% increase (to MGA 3,000) increases the NPV to MGA +9,822.37 million and the IRR to 15.75%. These results show that the project is very sensitive to price fluctuations. The project becomes profitable and attractive when the price is increased from 2000 MGA.

Figure 4. Influence Of Variable Electricity Prices on power plant profitability

3.2 Sensitivity two. Effect of change in Discount Rate

IRR remains constant at 10.37% independently of changes in the discount rate. On the other hand, NPV falls sharply as the discount rate increases, from a high positive value to a negative one. At a discount rate of 6%, NPV is very positive (9,937.07 MGA), indicating high profitability. At a discount rate of 8%, it falls to 4,237.4 MGA, then at 10% (base case), it's still positive (531.59 MGA). However, at a discount rate of 12%, NPV becomes negative

(-1,895.22 MGA), indicating insufficient profitability. NPV sensitivity shows a critical threshold between 10% and 12%, beyond which the project is no longer profitable.

Figure 5. Impact of changes in the discount rate on power plant profitability

3.3 Sensitivity Three. Effect of a change in the construction periods

The decrease in the price of electricity (2000 MGA to 1800 MGA) reflects a decrease in revenue per unit with the extension of the construction period. NPV increases with the extension: 531.91 MGA (2 years), 673.87 MGA (3 years), 737.23 MGA (5 years). IRR rises slightly: 10.37%, 10.49%, 10.59%. These trends indicate that a longer lead time optimizes project value by spreading investment more evenly and taking advantage of favorable long-term conditions. Extending the construction period thus appears more profitable, but a thorough analysis of costs and risks is recommended to validate this strategy.

Figure 6. Effects of different construction periods on project profitability

4. Discussion:

This study highlights the significant sensitivity of energy projects to fluctuations in electricity prices and discount rates. Despite an apparent stability in the Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which remains at 10.37%, when the discount rate is changed, this constancy conceals an underlying vulnerability. The economic value of the project, particularly the Net Present Value (NPV), exhibits substantial variation in response to tariff changes. This volatility indicates that the project's profitability is closely tied to the economic environment and the electricity market, raising questions about its long-term viability.

The analysis reveals that the NPV is especially responsive to price variations, prompting the need to consider strategies aimed at reducing this dependency. Among these, risk hedging through financial instruments and diversification of revenue streams emerge as effective solutions to enhance the project's resilience against market fluctuations. Implementing hedging strategies using derivatives or forward contracts can lock in prices and reduce exposure to unpredictable market movements. Similarly, diversifying income sources—such as integrating multiple renewable energy technologies or establishing long-term power purchase agreements (PPAs)—can stabilize revenues and mitigate risks associated with price volatility.

Furthermore, the study suggests that extending the construction period could optimize project value, provided that the long-term costs of financing and planning are controlled. A flexible schedule allows adaptation to evolving market conditions and technological advancements. Delaying completion might also provide opportunities to incorporate innovative technologies or benefit from favorable policy changes, thereby increasing the project's overall financial robustness.

In terms of technological innovation, integrating energy storage systems or establishing guaranteed long-term contracts (PPAs) could stabilize or even enhance electricity sale prices. Hybrid systems combining solar, wind, and storage technologies offer a promising avenue to reduce vulnerability to tariff fluctuations. These technological solutions can secure revenue streams and improve the financial stability of the project by balancing supply and demand more effectively, thus providing a buffer against market uncertainties.

The study also emphasizes the importance of digital platforms for real-time management of investments and risks. Digitalization enables better anticipation of market fluctuations, proactive risk management, and continuous performance optimization. Advanced data analytics and monitoring tools can provide actionable insights, allowing project operators to respond swiftly to changing conditions and maintain financial stability.

On the policy front, it is recommended that governments establish regulatory mechanisms to ensure electricity market stability. Measures such as guaranteed electricity prices or targeted subsidies can help buffer the impact of price fluctuations on project revenues. Such interventions create a more predictable environment, fostering investor confidence and encouraging the development of innovative projects.

Regulatory frameworks play a crucial role in creating conducive conditions for project success. Establishing clear, transparent regulations that facilitate access to financing, promote technological innovation, and streamline administrative procedures is essential. A stable regulatory environment reassures investors and supports the implementation of innovative strategies, ultimately enhancing the economic viability of energy projects.

However, this study relies on simplified assumptions, including linear scenarios of price fluctuations and project construction periods limited to two, three, or five years. It does not account for certain indirect costs, regulatory or environmental risks, or potential macroeconomic shocks. These limitations highlight the need for future research to deepen the understanding of risks and develop comprehensive mitigation strategies.

5. Conclusion

This study emphasizes the promising potential of solar photovoltaic plants for rural electrification in Madagascar, aligning with the Africa Energy Pact. It demonstrates that constructing a cost-effective 5.9 MW plant, selling electricity at 2,000 MGA/kWh, is feasible. Key to success is meticulous cost management and strategic pricing, as the project's current costs are near the break-even point of around 1,500 MGA. Financial analysis shows that the project's net present value remains positive at a discount rate up to 10%, but turns negative at 12%, highlighting a critical risk threshold. Incorporating the construction period enhances project value by balancing investments and slightly increasing IRR. The recommended solution is a mini-grid with lithium battery storage, with an investment of MGA 25 billion, capable of meeting demand for 25 years, expanding access, reducing carbon footprint, and allowing scalability for future needs. Future research should explore complex scenarios involving macroeconomic factors, risk management strategies, and innovative pilot projects using AI for dynamic decision-

making. Addressing implementation challenges such as funding, workforce training, and community engagement is essential for success. Overall, the study advocates for a comprehensive approach that combines technological innovation, supportive policies, and proactive risk management to ensure resilient, sustainable, and economically viable energy development capable of adapting to market and macroeconomic fluctuations, fostering long-term growth.

References

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